

Early-Onset dMMR Colon Cancer with Progression After Chemotherapy and Marked Response to Immunotherapy: A Case Report

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Introduction

Colorectal cancer in young adults is relatively uncommon but often presents at an advanced stage, with a tendency toward more aggressive clinical behaviour. In recent years, mismatch repair deficiency (dMMR) has become an important predictive biomarker for response to immunotherapy, especially in advanced disease.

Case Presentation

We present the case of a 22-year-old female with no significant past medical history who was diagnosed with sigmoid colon adenocarcinoma following imaging and colonoscopy, with histopathological confirmation. She underwent surgical resection, which showed a poorly differentiated tumour invading adjacent ileal loops (pT4bN1a, R1), with associated lymphovascular and perineural invasion. Given these high-risk features, adjuvant chemotherapy with CAPEOX was started. However, on follow-up imaging, disease progression was observed, with the development of peritoneal carcinomatosis and locoregional lymphadenopathy. Because of this progression, molecular profiling was performed, which showed a mismatch repair-deficient tumour with loss of MSH2 and MSH6 expression, along with a KRAS mutation. Based on these findings, treatment was switched to combined immunotherapy with nivolumab and ipilimumab, followed by maintenance nivolumab. The patient showed clinical improvement, with normalization of tumour markers and a noticeable reduction in peritoneal disease on imaging. Disease control has been maintained on follow-up. Treatment was generally well tolerated, with only mild immune-related thyroid dysfunction.

Conclusion

This case highlights the aggressive presentation of early-onset colorectal cancer and the surgical challenges associated with locally advanced disease. It also underscores the importance of molecular profiling in guiding treatment decisions, as dMMR tumours may respond favourably to immunotherapy even after progression on conventional chemotherapy.

Keywords

early-onset colorectal cancer; mismatch repair deficiency (dMMR); immunotherapy; peritoneal carcinomatosis